

EFFECTS OF GEOMETRY AND STACKING SEQUENCE ON APPARENT POISSON'S RATIO OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATE CFRPS UNDER THE COMPRESSION TESTS

E. Hara¹, H. Katoh¹, Y. Iwahori² and T. Yokozeki^{3*}

¹ Structures and Advanced Composite Research Unit, Aeronautical Technology Directorate, Japan aerospace exploration agency (JAXA), Tokyo, Japan, eichi12 @chofu.jaxa.jp

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Science and Technology, Meiji University, Tokyo, Japan,

³ Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, University of Tokyo, Tokyo, Japan

Keywords: Mechanical properties, Test method and Poisson's ratio.

ABSTRACT

To propose reasonable conditions for measuring the Poisson's ratio of a quasi-isotropic laminate plate, experimental compressive tests and finite element analyses were performed.

The effects of specimen geometry and stacking sequence on the Poisson's ratio of a quasi-isotropic carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer laminate were experimentally examined by compression tests. In particular, the divergence of the apparent Poisson's ratio from a theoretical value was experimentally measured for a decreasing specimen width/thickness ratio (b/t). The observed tendency was subsequently confirmed by simulations using finite element analysis (FEA). FEA was performed using a three-dimensional model of the specimens to investigate the strain and stress distribution. Moreover, in the evaluation of the apparent Poisson's ratio, the width direction strain was confirmed to vary under a low b/t . The FEA results confirmed that the cause of the changes to the width strain was the cross-sectional deformation under compressive loading, resulting from differences in the layer angles and stiffness between the outermost and inner layers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Poisson's ratio for quasi-isotropic laminates can be calculated with Equation (1) [1], derived from the Classical Lamination Theory and data regarding unidirectional properties.

$$\nu_{XY} = \frac{4G_{LT}(\nu_{LT}^2 E_T - E_L) + (6\nu_{LT} + 1)E_L E_T + E_L^2}{4G_{LT}(\nu_{LT}^2 E_T - E_L) - (2\nu_{LT} + 3)E_L E_T - 3E_L^2} \quad (1)$$

where E_L and E_T are the in-plane elastic moduli in the fiber direction and transverse direction, respectively. G_{LT} is the in-plane shear modulus. ν_{LT} is the in-plane Poisson's ratio of lamina. However, evaluating these properties from each UD specimen is relatively complex and expensive. Thus, it is useful to evaluate Poisson's ratio by performing experimental tests for laminate specimens directly. The practical reasons for measuring Poisson's ratio for quasi-isotropic laminates specimens are as follows:

- 1 It can be evaluated without measuring many properties of unidirectional lamina; and
- 2 The measured Poisson's ratio will be available for conceptual design by assuming the quasi-isotropic laminate to be a homogeneous material with respect to in-plane directions.

Moreover, it is useful to be able to measure Poisson's ratio by compression tests, although the measurement of Poisson's ratio is regulated in standardized tension tests. Thus, to study and propose the measurable conditions for evaluating the theoretical Poisson's ratio derived from classical lamination theory, experimental tests were carried out using 8 types of specimens. To predict the longitudinal strain, transverse strain, and apparent Poisson's ratio, finite element analyses (FEAs) with three-dimensional modelled specimens were also carried out. The mechanism underlying these apparent Poisson's ratio variations is discussed by observing the specimen deformation simulated with

FEA. In this study, Poisson's ratio that was measured or predicted with strains on the gauge section surfaces of quasi-isotropic laminate CFRP specimens, is described as the "apparent Poisson's ratio".

The superiority of the NAL-II compression method proposed by Ogasawara and Ishikawa [2] has been demonstrated. Thus, the NAL-II compression method for revising JIS K 2018: was applied in this study.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Material

CFRPs were fabricated from a unidirectional reinforcing fiber (T800S) and an epoxy matrix (3900-2B; supplied by TORAY, Japan). Quasi-isotropic laminate (the stacking sequence [(45/0/-45/90) 4] s; "QI32-bxx") was chosen as compression test specimens. Meanwhile, it was predicted that the stiffness in the width direction of the outer laminate (surface layer and its inner layer) of a specimen would affect the apparent Poisson's ratio and the cross-sectional deformation. Thus, a material of stacking sequence [(90/45/0/-45) 4] s;"QI32-R+45-bxx", which was rotated 45° from [(45/0/-45/90)4] s, was prepared.

2.2 Compression test specimen

Eight types of specimens were machined from the abovementioned laminates. Table 1 shows the parameters of the experiment, specimen dimensions, selected test fixture, and grid length of the strain gauge. The ratio of specimen width to specimen thickness is shown in Table 1 for discussion. The number of each test condition was five.

Table 1 Parameters of experiment, specimens, test fixture, grid length of strain gauge.

#	Specimen type	Number of ply	Nominal thickness (t)	Overall length (l_0)	Width (b)	Distance between support fixtures (L) [mm]	Width / thickness ratio (b/t)	Test fixture type	Grid length of strain gauge [mm]
1	QI32-b7	32	6.2	107	7	7	1.1	Regular	1
2	QI32-b10	32	6.2	110	10	10	1.6	Regular	1
3	QI32-b15	32	6.2	115	15	15	2.4	Regular	2
4	QI32-b25	32	6.2	125	25	25	4.0	Large	2
5	QI32-b38	32	6.2	138	38	38	6.1	Large	2
6	QI32-R+45-b7	32	6.2	107	7	7	1.1	Regular	1
7	QI32-R+45-b15	32	6.2	115	15	15	2.4	Regular	2
8	QI32-R+45-b38	32	6.2	138	38	38	6.1	Large	2

2.3 Compression test fixtures and test procedure.

Figure 1 shows the regular test fixture and specimen. The end-loading method was applied. Two types of test fixtures were used in this study. A regular test fixture and a large test fixture were used for specimens of widths 15 and 38 mm, respectively. Both of these test fixtures for restraining the specimen ends are 50-mm long. The tightening torque for the bolts shown in Figure 1 was approximately 0 N·m in this study. After setting the specimen on the supports and retainers in the setting fixture, the specimen with supports and retainers was moved in the sleeve. Compression loading was performed at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 1.0 mm /min. Compression force was loaded until the measuring strains necessary for calculating the apparent Poisson's ratio was obtained. Figure 2 shows the test setup and specimen. Tests were performed with Instron electromechanical universal testing systems.

Figure 1 Test fixture for compression tests (Regular type)

Figure 2 Example of test setup for compression (QI32-b15specimen / regular fixture).

2.4 Strain measurement.

Two biaxial strain gauges were glued to the front and back sides of the specimens; the centers of the strain gauges were located on the centers of the specimens. KFGS-2-120-D16 (grid length 2 mm) and KFGS-1-120-D16 (grid length 1 mm) supplied by Kyowa electronic instruments were used in this study. Table 1 shows the strain gauges used for each type of specimen.

2.5 Poisson's ratio calculation.

Poisson's ratio was calculated with Equation (2).

$$\nu = \left| \frac{\Delta\varepsilon_T}{\Delta\varepsilon_L} \right|, \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\varepsilon_T$ and $\Delta\varepsilon_L$ are the strain increments in the width and length directions of the specimen, respectively. The strain range for calculating Poisson's ratio was from 0.05% to 0.25% with reference to the calculating strain range of ISO 14126:1999.

3 FEA

The apparent Poisson's ratio in the loaded specimens were estimated using a commercial FEA program, ABAQUS 2016, under the assumption of a linear elastic response. The finite element models with three-dimensional hexahedral elements include the whole specimen. Figure 3 shows an overview of the FEA.

To simulate the loading conditions for the specimen, boundary conditions for the FEA models were assumed as follows:

- (1) Compressive mandatory displacement was applied on the top surface of the specimen. Mandatory displacements of 0.1% for each specimen length were applied.
- (2) Mandatory displacement in the longitudinal direction on the bottom surface of the specimen was 0.
- (3) The center point on the bottom surface was tied to X-Y-Z directional displacements.
- (4) Points at both ends in the width direction of the mid-plane surface in the thickness direction were tied to X-Z directional displacements.
- (5) Z-directional displacements on front/back surfaces facing the support and retainer parts of the test fixture were 0.

The in-plane size and thickness of the hexahedral elements were 0.5 mm and 0.195 mm, respectively. The stacking directions for each layer of the models were the same as those of the experimental specimens. Table 2 shows a list of FEA models.

The apparent Poisson's ratio was calculated from the FEA results as follows: longitudinal strains and transverse strain from FEA were calculated by dividing the distance of the node points corresponding to each strain gauge length before loading by the distance after loading. The apparent Poisson's ratio from FEA was calculated by dividing the transverse strain by the longitudinal strain.

Figure 3 Concept of finite element analysis.

Table 2 Parameters of additional finite element analysis (FEA) models.

#	Model name	Number of ply	Specimen dimensions [mm]			Distance between support fixtures (L) [mm]	Width / thickness ratio (b/t)
			Nominal thickness (t)	Overall length (l_0)	Width (b)		
1	QI32-b7	32	6.24	107	7	7	1.1
2	QI32-b10	32	6.24	110	10	10	1.6
3	QI32-b15	32	6.24	115	15	15	2.4
4	QI32-b25	32	6.24	125	25	25	4.0
5	QI32-b38	32	6.24	138	38	38	6.1
6	QI32-R+45-b7	32	6.24	107	7	7	1.1
7	QI32-R+45-b10	32	6.24	110	10	10	1.6
8	QI32-R+45-b15	32	6.24	115	15	15	2.4
9	QI32-R+45-b25	32	6.24	125	25	25	4.0
10	QI32-R+45-b38	32	6.24	138	38	38	6.1

4 RESULTS

4.1 Experimental results

Figure 4 shows the typical experimental stress–strain curves. FL and BL denote the longitudinal strains of the front side and back side, respectively, while FT and BT are the transverse strains of the front and back sides, respectively. The front and back sides faced the test fixture “retainer” and “support”, respectively. Error bars in the figure indicate the maximum and minimum data. Figure 5 shows the apparent Poisson’s ratio as a function of the b/t ratio. The theoretical value in Figure 5 was calculated by substituting lamina data [1] for equation (1) derived from the classical lamination theory. With increasing width b , the apparent Poisson ratio approaches the theoretical value. It was confirmed that the apparent Poisson’s ratio is close to the theoretical value when $b/t > 4$.

Figure 4 Typical experimental stress–strain curves. (Specimen: QI32-b15)

Figure 5 Apparent Poisson’s ratio by experiments as a function of specimen width/thickness ratio b/t .

4.2 Results of FEA

Figure 6 shows the apparent Poisson's ratio from the results of FEA as a function of the specimen b/t ratio. Figures 7 and 8 show the longitudinal strain and transverse strain from FEA as a function of the b/t ratio, respectively. With decreasing specimen width, the apparent Poisson's ratio increased. Figure 6 shows that the apparent Poisson's ratio increases with decreasing b/t ratio. Figure 8 thus suggests that the primary factor affecting how the apparent Poisson's ratio varied with b/t was the increasing transverse strain.

Figure 6 Apparent Poisson's ratio from the results of FEA as a function of the specimen b/t ratio.

Figure 7 Strains in the width direction of FEA results.

Figure 8 Strains in the longitudinal direction of FEA results.

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Comparison between experimental results and FEA

Figure 9 shows the apparent Poisson's ratio from experimental and FEA results as a function of the specimen b/t ratio. With decreasing b/t ratio, the apparent Poisson's ratios of the [(45/0/-45/90)₄] s; "QI32" specimen increased. The tendency shown by the experiment results agree with the FEA results, although the experimental results exhibited lower values than the FEA results. In particular, the apparent Poisson's ratio of the "QI32" material increased significantly when $b/t < 4$.

Meanwhile, the apparent Poisson's ratio of the [(90/45/0/-45)₄] s; "QI32-R+45" specimens are lower than the theoretical value. The reduced strain in the width direction compared with the theoretical value may have been caused by the reduced cross-sectional deformations around the outer layer of the specimen under compressive loading. The apparent Poisson's ratio of the "QI32-R+45" material decreased significantly when $b/t < 4$.

Figure 9 Apparent Poisson's ratio from experimental and FEA results as a function of specimen b/t ratio.

5.2 Effect of deformation of cross-section of specimen gauge area on apparent Poisson's ratio.

Figures 10 and 11 show the displacement contour for the thickness direction of the cross sections of the "QI32-b7" and "QI32-R+45-b7" models, respectively. The Y direction and Z direction correspond to the specimen width and thickness directions, respectively, in these figures.

In Figure 10, the uneven shapes on the free edges was caused by the non-restriction by each layer and the different in-plane Poisson's ratio for each layer. The reason for the small 90° layer deformations was the low Poisson's ratio ν_{TL} .

Because of differences in deformation in the thickness direction, as shown in Figure 10, the length in the width direction on the front and back side surfaces of the "QI32-bxx" specimen were expanded. The extension of this length in the width direction on the specimen surfaces generates a higher strain in the width direction than that assumed with the classical lamination theory. The apparent Poisson's ratio of the compression specimens machined into finite dimensions from a large test plate, configured as [(45/0/-45/90) n] s, was measured as higher than the theoretical value.

Figure 11 shows the displacement contour of the QI32-R+45-b7 model, as mentioned above. The apparent Poisson's ratio of the [(90/45/0/-45)4] s; "QI32-R+45-bxx" specimens are lower than the theoretical value. The reduced strain in the width direction compared with the theoretical value may have been caused by reduced cross-sectional deformations around the outer layer of the specimen, as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 10 Contour of displacement in the Z direction on cross section of center plane (QI32-b7).

Figure 11 Contour of displacement in the Z direction on cross section of center plane (QI32-R+45-b7).

6 CONCLUSION

Experiments and FEA were performed to investigate the dimensions of specimens necessary for measuring the apparent Poisson's ratio close to the theoretical value in compression tests of quasi-isotropic laminate specimens.

(1) The effect of specimen geometry and stacking sequence on the apparent Poisson's ratio was confirmed from the experimental and FEA results.

(2) The apparent Poisson's ratio deviated from the theoretical value. It was confirmed that the tendency of divergence with a low b/t ratio depended on the specimen stacking sequence under a low width/thickness ratio, b/t . It was experimentally confirmed that the apparent Poisson's ratio was higher than the theoretical value in the case of [(45/0/-45/90) 4] s and lower than the theoretical value in the case of [(90/45/0/-45) 4] s. A similar tendency was simulated using FEA.

(3) FEA results suggested that the primary cause of the divergence of the apparent Poisson's ratio was the increasing or decreasing strain in the specimen width direction. Results reflecting this estimate were experimentally confirmed.

(4) Moreover, it was confirmed with FEA results that the causes of increasing or decreasing strain in the specimen width direction were cross-sectional deformations.

(5) The apparent Poisson's ratio was similar to the theoretical value when $b/t > 4$, although this result was limited under conditions of material, stacking sequence, and number of ply in this study. FEA results suggested that the b/t condition necessary for the apparent Poisson's ratio to be close to the theoretical value was affected by the dimension ratio of the specimen and by the stiffness relationship between the outer layer and inner layer.

REFERENCES

- [1] Eiichi Hara, Hisaya Katoh, Yutaka Iwahori and Tomohiro Yokozeki, Influence of Specimen Geometry on Apparent Poisson's Ratio Evaluated under the Compressive Loading of Quasi-Isotropic CFRP Laminate, J. of the Japan Society for Composite Materials, Vol.45, No.2, 2019, pp. 72-82 (in Japanese).
- [2] Toshio Ogasawara, Takashi Ishikawa, Advanced Composite Materials, Vol.25, No.S1, pp131-145, 2016.